

DSWG.LO.005
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HIP Double Star Annex (Version 2)

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1. Introduction

A previous note (DSWG.Lo.004) gave some general considerations on the design of the double star annex (DSA) to the output catalogue. This was discussed at the DSWG meeting in Brussels (11 March 1994), and the present note gives a slightly updated proposal, now also for the machine-readable version.

I have retained the philosophy of the first version, in particular the use of 'normal points' consisting of a (roughly independent) estimate of the position and proper motion of a component at a specified epoch.

2. Content of the printed DSA

Part of a sample page with fictitious data is attached. The content of each field (1–23) is as follows:

- 1 System identifier, e.g.. a CCDM number
- 2 Component identifier: ‘a’ for the primary, ‘b’ for the secondary, etc. This may or may not correspond to the components labelled ‘A’, ‘B’, etc, in HIC Annex 1
- 3 Entry number in the main catalogue. Note that a given entry may be resolved into several components in the DSA
- 4 Epoch to which all the remaining data (fields 5–22) refer, expressed as the Julian date
- 5 Barycentric right ascension (RA) at the epoch of field 4, in the reference frame ERF 2000, α
- 6 Barycentric declination (Dec) at the epoch of field 4, in the reference frame ERF 2000, δ
- 7 Proper motion in RA at the epoch of field 4, in the reference frame ERF 2000, $\mu_{\alpha*} = \mu_{\alpha} \cos \delta$
- 8 Proper motion in Dec at the epoch of field 4, in the reference frame ERF 2000, μ_{δ}
- 9 Trigonometric parallax, π
- 10 Standard error of the position in RA, $\sigma_{\alpha*} = \sigma_{\alpha} \cos \delta$
- 11 Standard error of the position in Dec, σ_{δ}
- 12 Correlation coefficient, ρ_{α}^{δ}
- 13 Standard error of the proper motion in RA, $\sigma_{\mu_{\alpha*}} = \sigma_{\mu_{\alpha}} \cos \delta$
- 14 Standard error of the proper motion in Dec, $\sigma_{\mu_{\delta}}$
- 15 Correlation coefficient, $\rho_{\mu_{\alpha*}}^{\mu_{\delta}}$
- 16 Standard error of trigonometric parallax, σ_{π}
- 17 Median magnitude in the photometric system H_p
- 18 ‘V’ = flag indicating that the component is variable
- 19 Standard error of the median magnitude, σ_{H_p}
- 20 Colour index (from ground-based observations) used for the reductions, $V-I$
- 21 Approximate position angle of the component relative to the component specified in field 23, θ
- 22 Approximate distance from the component specified in field 23, ρ
- 23 Component to which the relative position in fields 21–22 refers

The dotted lines signify items that are common to two or more components or normal points. In such cases the relevant value is found immediately above the dots.

3. Content of the electronic DSA

The machine-readable DSA contains identically the same data as in the first 20 fields of the printed version, plus additional correlations. The printed data in fields 21-23 (approximate relative position) are not copied to the electronic DSA, as they can be computed to full precision from the other data. The lower-case letters designating the components ('a', 'b', etc) are translated to upper-case in the electronic version.

For each system there is a header record followed by two or more data records, and (optionally) a number of cross-correlation records. The data records essentially correspond to the individual lines of the printed DSA, while the cross-correlation records contain the correlation coefficients *between* the data records.

The header records contains the system identifier (CCDM number or similar) and the three integers *ncomp* (number of components), *ndata* (number of data records), and *ncorr* (number of cross-correlation records). The data and cross-correlation records are sequentially numbered (1, 2, ..., *ndata*) and (1, 2, ..., *ncorr*), respectively.

A data record (corresponding to a normal point) contains six estimated parameters: ($\alpha, \delta, \mu_{\alpha^*}, \mu_{\delta}, \pi, Hp$), the corresponding six standard errors and 15 correlation coefficients.

A cross-correlation record contains 36 correlation coefficients corresponding to all pair-wise combinations of the six parameters in two different data records. The second and third field in the cross-correlation record specify which two data records are being considered. There can be at most $ndata \times (ndata - 1)/2$ cross-correlation records.

Note that this format allows complete specification of the full variance-covariance matrix of arbitrarily complex systems with multiple normal points. For instance, in system 20514-0537 there are two components each with two normal points, thus four data records with a total of 24 estimated parameters. The variance-covariance matrix is specified by 24 standard errors (contained in the data records) and $24 \times (24 - 1)/2 = 276$ correlation coefficients. The latter are contained partly in the four data records ($4 \times 15 = 60$ coefficients), partly in the six cross-correlation records ($6 \times 36 = 216$ coefficients).

Naturally, not all of the $6 \times ndata$ parameters of a given system need to be independently estimated. For instance, the parallax is assumed to be the same in the four data records of 20514-0537. This implies that (1) the parallax standard error is the same in all four data records, and (2) the corresponding six cross-correlations are equal to +1.00. This gives a partially degenerate variance-covariance matrix, but there is no formal difficulty in handling this.

20^h 51^m - 21^h 06^m
 102921 - 107945

CCDM 1	Component 2	HIP 3	Epoch J1900+ year 4	Position at Epoch		Proper Motion		Par. π mas 9	Astrometric Errors and Corr.						Mag. & Colour				Rel. Pos.					
				α deg 5	δ deg 6	μ_{α^*} mas/yr 7	μ_{δ} mas/yr 8		σ_{α^*} mas 10	σ_{δ} mas 11	ρ_{α}^{δ} 12	$\sigma_{\mu_{\alpha^*}}$ mas/yr 13	$\sigma_{\mu_{\delta}}$ mas/yr 14	$\rho_{\mu_{\alpha^*}}^{\mu_{\delta}}$ 15	σ_{π} mas 16	Hp mag 17	V mag 18	σ_{Hp} mag 19	V-I mag 20	θ deg 21	ρ arcsec 22	R 23		
20512+5126	a	102921	91.173	312.782	293 70	+51.432	876 19	-52.3	41.7	38.5	2.7	3.3	-0.08	0.5	1.3	-0.22	2.0	7.301	0.009	0.795	36	0.91	a	
	b	102921	91.173	312.782	401 27	+51.432	711 21	-51.1	41.9		6.5	8.5	-0.12	2.6	2.9	-0.25		10.048	0.067	0.795				
20514-0537	a	102945	90.470	312.793	393 70	-05.459	676 19	96.5	-7.1	9.1	3.1	3.6	+0.10	2.1	2.0	+0.18	3.0	6.4	V	0.16	0.376			
	b	102945	92.398	312.793	397 35	-05.459	678 89	94.1	-7.8		3.5	3.5	-0.02	3.6	3.2	+0.07								
			90.470	312.793	500 47	-05.459	510 30	85.2	13.9		8.6	9.5	+0.20	3.8	3.9	+0.14		7.582	0.075	0.376	219	0.33	a	
			92.398	312.793	504 21	-05.459	512 92	88.7	11.8		7.9	10.1	+0.19	5.7	5.2	+0.29						222	0.34	a
20531+2909	a	103074	90.391	313.023	239 81	+29.156	212 23	-130.2	210.5	105.2	1.9	2.1	-0.15	2.5	2.8	-0.12	1.1	8.212	0.006	1.012				
			92.155	313.023	241 16	+29.156	331 95	-125.1	213.6		2.0	2.2	-0.10	2.7	3.1	+0.02								
21014-7526	a	103745	91.314	315.012	301 81	-75.391	376 19	52.3	-64.1	5.1	2.7	3.3	-0.07	0.5	1.3	-0.22	2.0	8.510	0.019	0.108				
	b	103747	91.314	315.012	118 17	-75.391	811 21	91.1	13.2	-1.1	6.5	8.5	-0.12	2.6	2.9	-0.28	2.4	9.73	V	0.07	0.477	157	13.01	a
21114+3526	a	104510	91.112	315.012	301 81	+35.391	376 19	22.3	-11.5	3.1	3.7	3.3	+0.01	2.2	1.9	-0.05	2.1	9.610	0.049	0.501				
	b	104510	91.112	315.012	118 17	+35.391	811 21											11.933	0.150	0.501	29	3.81	a	
21514-1529	a	107624	91.240	315.754	271 04	-15.482	117 88	196.5	-81.9	49.1	2.0	1.8	-0.15	2.5	2.2	+0.07	2.4	6.391	0.021	0.814				
	b	107624	91.240	315.754	118 38	-15.482	141 20	196.7	-83.2		2.8	2.5	-0.11	3.1	3.0	-0.02		7.582	0.087	0.814	341	15.51	a	
	c	107624	91.240	315.753	845 51	-15.482	333 46	188.9	-81.0		4.9	4.2	-0.09	5.2	5.0	-0.19		7.912	0.121	0.814	102	0.83	b	

Electronic DS Annex: Draft Format

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20512+5126 2 2 1
1 A 102921 91.173 312.78229370 +51.43287619 -52.3 41.7 38.5 2.7 3.3 0.5 1.3 2.0 7.301 0.009 0.795 -0.08 (14 more correlations)
2 B 102921 91.173 312.78240127 +51.43271121 -51.1 41.9 38.5 6.5 8.5 2.6 2.9 2.0 10.048 0.067 0.795 -0.12 (14 more correlations)
1 1 2 +0.20 -0.12 -0.18 (33 more cross-correlations)
20514-0537 2 4 6
1 A 102945 90.470 312.79339370 -05.45967619 96.5 -7.1 9.1 3.1 3.6 2.1 2.0 3.0 6.400 V 0.160 0.376 +0.10 (14 more correlations)
2 A 102945 92.398 312.79339735 -05.45967889 94.1 -7.8 9.1 3.5 3.6 3.2 3.0 6.400 V 0.160 0.376 +0.10 (14 more correlations)
3 B 102945 90.470 312.79350047 -05.45951030 85.2 13.9 9.1 8.6 9.5 3.8 3.9 3.0 7.582 0.075 0.376 +0.20 (14 more correlations)
4 B 102945 92.398 312.79350421 -05.45951292 88.7 11.8 9.1 7.9 10.1 5.7 5.2 3.0 7.582 0.075 0.376 +0.19 (14 more correlations)
1 1 2 -0.06 -0.08 +0.14 (33 more cross-correlations)
2 1 3 +0.18 -0.25 -0.21 (33 more cross-correlations)
3 1 4 +0.13 +0.05 -0.30 (33 more cross-correlations)
4 2 3 -0.31 +0.45 -0.55 (33 more cross-correlations)
5 2 4 -0.30 -0.23 -0.13 (33 more cross-correlations)
6 3 4 +0.02 +0.12 -0.10 (33 more cross-correlations)
20531+2909 1 2 1
1 A 103074 90.391 313.02323981 +29.15621223 -130.2 210.5 105.2 1.9 2.1 2.5 2.8 1.1 8.212 0.006 1.012 -0.15 (14 more correlations)
2 A 103074 92.155 313.02324116 +29.15633195 -125.1 213.6 105.2 2.0 2.2 2.7 3.1 1.1 8.212 0.006 1.012 -0.10 (14 more correlations)
1 1 2 +0.03 -0.02 +0.11 (33 more cross-correlations)
```

Data content for each system:

```
CCDM ncomp ndata ncorr
for idata = 1 to ndata:
  idata icomp HIC epoch ra dec pmra pmdec par sd_ra sd_dec sd_pmra sd_pmdec sd_par Hp flag_var sd Hp vmi ((corr(i,j), j=i+1,6), i=1,6)
for icorr = 1 to ncorr:
  icorr idata1 idata2 ((corr(i), i=1,36))
```

Complete specification of all correlations requires $n_{corr} = n_{data} * (n_{data} - 1) / 2$.